

THE EFFECT OF MALOCCLUSION ON SLEEP-RELATED BREATHING DISORDERS FOR CHILDREN

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Introduction: The full and timely development of a child is influenced by many factors, one of which is a healthy sleep. According to statistics from the German Sleep Society, 21-37% of children and adolescents have sleep disorders, and only 15-18% of parents seek help from a specialist. The significance of this study lies in the fact that respiratory disorders (snoring, partially combined with apnea, obstructive sleep apnea) can be caused by a number of organic causes, such as otolaryngological (adenoids, enlarged palatine tonsils) or dental (distal mandible or "Gothic" shape of the palate) disorders of the upper respiratory tract, however, the reason for this is that they are not considered important for diagnosis.

Objective: to identify occlusal abnormalities affecting sleep-related breathing disorders in children. Objectives 1) To increase the level of differential diagnosis of the causes of sleep disorders; 2) To identify the main occlusal abnormalities affecting respiratory disorders and methods of their correction.

Materials and methods: clinical intraoral photographs and cone beam computed tomography (CBCT), assessment of the volume of the respiratory tract in children before and after orthodontic treatment using palatal dilators at the age of 12 years. **Conclusions:**

1) Differential diagnosis requires interdisciplinary collaboration between pediatricians, otolaryngologists, and dentists.

2) Anamnesis collection is important to identify the organic causes of shortness of breath and daytime fatigue in children. A sleep diary, which a parent

must complete within two weeks, is also useful for collecting medical history. Modern diagnostic tools such as CBCT should be used to assess the volume of the respiratory tract and the cause of stenosis.2) The main dental factors in the development of the problem under consideration are maxillary bone stenosis and the distal position of the mandible. Orthodontic treatment can be achieved by enlarging the upper jaw and moving the lower jaw forward using a functionally functioning bicuspid growth stimulation device.

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